

Unveiling Agricultural Odes with the aid of *Thirukkural*: A Bio-centric Study in the works of Munro and Bond

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Abstract

This study delves into the significant thematic intersections of farming, agriculture, and environment found in the select short stories of two distinguished authors, Alice Munro and Ruskin Bond. It discovers how these literary stalwarts employ the backdrop of rural life, farming, and the natural world to illustrate deeper human experiences. Alice Munro's stories frequently take place in rural Canada, where farming and agriculture play an important role in the lives of the people. Her stories depict the fortitude and perseverance of humans confronted with natural problems, underlining the inherent link between mankind and the land. Similarly, Ruskin Bond's stories set in the Indian countryside generate a sense of nostalgia and a longing for simplicity. His stories demonstrate the peaceful cohabitation of humans and the environment, emphasising the need to protect our natural surroundings. Also, in Tamil literature, Thiruvalluvar has portrayed the importance of nature and environment in his work Thirukkural. Under the section "Porul" which means Wealth, in the subchapter "Kudiyiyal" meaning 'Domestic Virtue', Valluvar highlights the interconnection of humans with nature. He gives importance to agriculture, farming and the importance of a balanced environment in that chapter. By touching on the references from "Tirukkural", one can understand the need for nature in harmony to keep our lives in harmony. Bond and Munro also have the same viewpoint regarding nature. The short stories taken up for study are Munro's "Dear Life," "Labor Day Dinner," "In Sight of Lake," and "Lichen," and Bond's "Blue Umbrella," "Summer Season," "As Times Goes By," and "Growing Up with Trees". This article highlights how Munro and Bond skilfully integrate rural life, occupation and nature into their narratives to emphasise the value of humans' relationship with land and environment.

Keywords: Rural Life, Human-Nature Relationship, Eco-Conscious, Short Stories, Alice Munro, Ruskin Bond, *Thirukkural*

Introduction

Every author possesses an exceptional ability to render realistic rural landscapes and underscore the enduring significance of farming and agriculture within the captivating realm of literature. Alice Munro and Ruskin Bond adeptly weave narratives that pay homage to man's interwoven relationship with the natural world. This study scrutinizes the works of these celebrated authors, delving into the underlying themes of farming, agriculture, and the

portrayal of nature that permeate their storytelling. Munro and Bond offer readers profound insights into the enduring relevance of these themes, prompting reflection on the indispensable connection between lives and the land from which narratives spring. Similarly, Thiruvalluvar in his magnum opus, *Thirukkural* highlights the importance of agriculture, farmers, and the essential elements for survival. Valluvar emphasizes the significance of water, plains, and trees for safety and sustenance, stating, “A fort is that which owns fount of waters crystal clear; An open space, a hill, and shade of beauteous forest near (Kural 742)” (90). This inquiry delves into the works of Bond and Munro by unveiling the intricate portrayal of nature and affirming the ongoing importance of preserving land.

Method and Approach of the Study

The descriptive and comparative approach has been used for the study. A few selected short stories by Alice Munro and Ruskin Bond and a few selected “Thirukkural” couplets have been taken for the research to know about the importance and value of agriculture, farming and nature. The study also focuses on Biocentrism where both man and nature are equally important for survival at the present times.

Theoretical Framework

The multidisciplinary field of eco-criticism studies binds the connection between the environment and literature. On the other hand, biocentrism is a theoretical viewpoint that highlights the interconnection of all life and holds that all living things have fundamental value. Biocentrism proposes that ethical and environmental issues should be centred on the health of ecosystems and living beings. It will be useful at the present times full of nature-orientated problems and human-related sustainability to resurrect them again.

Review of Literature

A. Jayasree, (2017) in the article “Nature, Nostalgia and Green Insights in Ruskin Bond’s *When You Can’t Climb Trees Anymore* and *In Search of Sweet-Peas*” confers about how Ruskin Bond gives importance to Nature and emphasises nostalgic insights intermingling in his short stories. The author also describes the closeness of Ruskin Bond with nature and his simple way of writing short stories where he talks about childhood memories, travelling in trains, and gardening. He connects people with nature which is the best part of his short stories.

Vaidhya has conducted a PhD research in the works of Ruskin Bond under the title, “Environmental concerns in Ruskin Bonds select short stories” in the year 2018. The scholar has found that throughout his works, especially in his short stories, Bond shows extraordinary concern for the life of fauna and flora of the regions that he experienced as a child. Bond shows concern for the environment including trees, animals, and birds. His concern also extends to smaller life forms such as reptiles and insects. The scholar concludes that Bond can rightly be considered a pioneer writer of Indian literature which is focused on environmental concerns.

Anitha conducted doctoral research in the year, 2020 under the title, “Fiction of Alice Munro a Study of Theme and Form” in which the researcher finds that Munro’s themes depict the life of small-town people, the relationship between human beings and nature, life and death, love and heartbreak, interpersonal dynamics in families and small communities. The scholar finds that Munro is more concerned with the emotional life experience of people instigated by memories and how people negotiate their lives with joy, sorrow, and longing.

In the article titled, “Considering All (Non) Living Things: A Biocentric Orientation in Blair Richmond’s *The Lithia Trilogy*”, Ida Farida Sachmandi and et al. remarks “Biocentrism says that people have to view life, including nature and humans, in a more holistic conception” (88).

In the article titled, “Agriculture in *Thirukkural*,” by Anuradha in the year 2019, depicts the importance given to agriculture and farming in the work *Thirukkural* by Valluvar. Further, the researcher describes the importance of agriculture and the farmers in the means of developing the society, where she also says that the country’s development or destruction lies in the hands of farmers.

The article titled, “Thiruvalluvar’s Concept of Cultural Ecology,” by G. Rajeswari in the year 2020, portrays the relationship between man and environment. Thiruvalluvar’s *Thirukkural* is the main concept of the article which describes nature and human’s dependency on water for survival. The article also deals with how the modern world and sophisticated life left nature which led them to environmental issues and disasters. The researcher also highlights how *Thirukkural* has portrayed the issues of nature and recommends an idyllic relationship between man and nature.

The article titled, “Thiruvalluvar’s Observation on Nature: A Study on the Classical Tamil Text *Thirukkural*”, by M. Kalaiarasan in the year 2018, portrayed how Thiruvalluvar has a unique bond with nature that helped him to write *Thirukkural* about the bond between man and nature. Furthermore, the researcher brings out the importance of trees, animals, water and birds in this world, where he mentions the world is equally important for all living beings.

G. Thirumoorthy’s article titled “Critical Review of Geographical Thoughts and Environmental Insight in *Thirukkural*” in the year 2021, portrays the importance of geographical representation which is thoroughly connected with language, development and migration. The researcher further explores the geographical information used in literature and also analyses how people have an understanding and gratitude for geographical representation.

The article titled, “The Tradition of the Farming People” by Pandi in the year 2019 represented the tradition of the people who do farming and agriculture for the betterment of society. Further, the researcher says that without farmers there will be no existence of humans and also says that the tradition of the farmers is considered to be the tradition of all the people, where he also referred to *Tholkappium* for a better understanding.

Objectives

- To explore how Alice Munro and Ruskin Bond’s literary works, depict farming and agriculture as integral elements of rural life in Canada and India.
- To examine the similarities and differences in the literary treatment of farming and agriculture between Munro and Bond with the aid of *Thirukkural*.
- To examine how these authors use nature and agricultural settings as a backdrop to convey deeper themes and emotions in their writings.

Cultivating Life and Embracing Nature

Agriculture and farming have had a tremendous impact on small-town people. Residents of small towns rely largely on the land and the agricultural industry for food and a means of sustenance. Agriculture contributes to the economics, ecology, and social fabric of

rural areas in ways other than crop production and animal keeping. There is a saying in *Thirukkural* by Valluvar, where he says, “The ploughers are the linch-pin of the world; they bear, Them up whom other works perform, too weak its toils to share (Kural 1032)” (124), that the farmers are the backbone of the whole world, where they also work for other people. Agriculture allows neighbours to interact, share resources, and assist one another. Aside from attracting residents, the agricultural industry also attracts tourists and visitors who want to experience rural life and learn about agriculture. Farmers also regularly preserve marshes, woodlands, and open areas that serve as wildlife habitats and contribute to the region’s natural beauty. Agriculture and farming are, in the end, essential parts of small-town people. Likewise, in the article titled, “The Need and Approach of Biocentrism in Amitav Ghosh *The Hungry Tide*”, Meenakshi and Shruti Soni remark, “Biocentrism is an ethical frame of view that extends inherent value to all living things, both in political and ecological sense, as we as literally. It’s knowledge of how the world functions, especially about its biosphere and biodiversity” (248). Alice Munro has always placed her stories amidst rural settings where there is farming, gardening, and agricultural activities happen alongside life experience. (Naddi 27) Bond is also in the habit of placing his stories amidst rural environs in which invariably all activities of human existence revolve around farming and agriculture (Beniwal 117)

The idea of farming and agriculture is conveyed in Alice Munro’s short story “Dear Life,” where the narrator’s father has a large field to produce crops and room for animals. The twelve acres of grass area, which is flanked by elm trees, serves as both shelter and food for the animals. Understanding the value of farming and agriculture, the narrator assists her father in caring for the fields and cattle by bringing them water and cleaning their shelter. Munro addresses the importance of farming and agriculture in small-town life via the characters of the narrator and her father. Agriculture and farming have cultural importance in small communities. In the article titled, “Thiruvalluvar’s Concept of Cultural Ecology,” Rajeswari opines about the importance of water and land for agriculture:

The wealth of water and land is important for the survival, where water and land are basic necessity. It is important for the humans to take care and increase the wealth of water and land, which is said in *Sirupanjamoolam, Elathi, Thirikadugam, Naaladiyaar*. Likewise, Valluvar’s *Thirukkural* also opines the same in the kural, “ A fort is that which owns fount of waters crystal clear; An open space, a hill, and shade of beauteous forest near. (Kural 742) (208)

Correspondingly, Binya in Ruskin Bond’s short story “Blue Umbrella” loves farming and her cows, and her house is surrounded by fields and gardens, “potatoes, onions, ginger, beans, mustard and maize” (Bond 182). She owns two cows, which she has called Neelu and Gori to symbolise her undying love for them. Her fields are overflowing with vegetables such as potatoes, onions, ginger, beans, mustard, and maize. Even if the veggies she raises are insufficient to sell at the market, they are sufficient to feed her family. Bond, via the character of Binya, emphasises the necessity of raising crops and vegetables, even if it is not enough to sell in the market but is sufficient to support her own family. In both the short stories, both the characters have an interest in farming and agriculture which leads them to cultivate their natural resources for living, where the narrator and Binya understand the importance of agriculture which is the main source of living.

Alice Munro's short story "Labour Day Dinner" delves into the value of farming through the character George, who is inspired by Valerie's home, which has a garden surrounded by plants and trees, "Valerie's front yard, under the shade of two aloof and splendid elm trees that have been expensively preserved. The grass underneath them has been kept green all summer and is bordered by fiery dahlias" (Munro 134). George purchases a home and property in a small town and begins farming by producing various veggies and fruits. Roberta creates jam from raspberries picked in their field. Roberta also assists George in the fields by caring for the plants and trees. George works on the farm and in the woods, and he never asks for help, demonstrating his love of farming. Agriculture and farming contribute to environmental protection. Likewise, the character of Visni in Ruskin Bond's short tale "Summer Season" emphasises the value of working on their farm and little town. He works at a theatre, and while he is content with his earnings, something makes him uneasy, and he wishes to return to his village and care for his farm. Visni decides to return to his land, his village, which reveals the genuine nature of small-town inhabitants and teaches Visni the value of agriculture, "It was his house, and his fields; even the snow was his" (Bond 97). Despite the variations between the two short stories, the necessity of agriculture is depicted when George and Visni learn that agriculture is not a hobby but a lifetime commitment which enriches their source of living. Likewise, Valluvar in *Thirukkural* says, "Who ploughing eat their food, they truly live; The rest to others bend subservient, eating what they give (Kural 1033)" (124), where he portrays that the people who do farming does not have to depend for food on others, rather people who do not do farming have to depend on the farmers for their daily needs.

The presentation of nature and environment in the life of small-town people has been a prominent theme in literature. Small towns are often depicted as idyllic, pastoral and closely connected to the natural world. Small towns often offer a unique representation of nature and the environment, one that is different from urban areas. These towns are usually situated near natural landscapes such as forests, lakes, and rivers, which play a vital role in shaping the character and identity of the community. One of the most notable features of small-town nature representation is the emphasis on preserving the natural environment. Small towns often have a strong sense of community, and residents take pride in maintaining the beauty and cleanliness of their surroundings. This is evident in the careful upkeep of parks and green spaces, as well as the protection of wildlife habitats. Ashmika Rai in her thesis titled, "Call for Biocentrism in Ursula K. Le Guin's *The Word for World Is Forest*" opines, "Biocentrism refers to the world where every living and non-living thing stay in the universe maintain a balance and harmonious relation" (28). Another key aspect of small-town nature representation is how it is integrated into daily life. In contrast to urban areas, where nature is often seen as a luxury or escape from city life, small towns incorporate nature into everyday routines and this is reflected in Munro's works (Naddi 27) and Bond's stories (Saklani 26).

Alice Munro's short story "In Sight of the Lake" deliberates on the theme of representation of nature, where the protagonist Nancy is an enthusiast of nature. The exquisiteness of nature incites her aesthetic sense because of her beautiful kinship with nature. She visits Highman village, a small town where she has to see a doctor, meanwhile, she also checks the village, to whether she can lead her life there because of her love towards nature and the small town. Small towns are the place where nature is unified into daily life.

Nancy admires every part of the Highman village, and she is amazed by the houses in the small town which is surrounded by gardens. She visits one of the gardens where the garden is filled with flowers, “In between the paths, and bursting from the grass, there are flowers. She knows some of them— the dark gold and light-yellow daisies for instance, pink and rosy and red-hearted white phlox” (Munro223), and comes to know that it is a private garden, which makes her dream about having a house with a garden in a small town. The way Nancy is admired by nature is that sometimes she forgets about herself. She visits a lake near the Highman village, where she feels the cool breeze around the place. Nancy is totally into nature, and she wants to spend the rest of her life in the small town. Similarly, Ruskin Bond’s short story “As Time Goes By” discusses the narrator’s love for lakes, rivers and waterfalls. The narrator is dragged to the sound of rain and he steps into the forest to feel the breeze of the rain and trees. When he hears the sound of the waterfalls, he follows the sound and finds a waterfall which has formed a pool, “Water trickled down from the hillside, from amongst ferns and grass and wildflowers; and the hills, rising steeply on either side, kept the ravine in the shadow” (Bond 79). Without any second thought, the narrator jumps into the pool and enjoys the waterfall, where Bond discusses aesthetic sense and love for the nature of the small-town people. The narrator not only enjoys himself but also brings his friends Somi and Dal to the pool. They spent their whole day in the forest by swimming, playing and riding buffaloes. In both the short stories, the theme representation of nature is depicted through the characters of Nancy and the narrator, who have abundant love for nature.

The short story “Lichen” by Alice Munro confers the theme of representation of nature through an old age home which shows the small-town people’s love for nature. The name of the old age home is ‘Balm of Gilead Home’, which they have named after the name of the tree which is called Balm of Gilead trees. The corridors of the old age home are painted green in colour which represents the colour of nature. Meanwhile, Stella’s house is also surrounded by plants and trees, “a jungle of wild blackberry bushes” (Munro 32), where she spends most of the time close to nature and the environment. Furthermore, Stella’s house is surrounded by mountains and beaches where most people love to spend their life. Similarly, the short story “Growing Up with Trees” by Ruskin Bond also delineates the theme of representation of nature through the narrator who grew up watching his grandfather grow trees around his house, “peepul, neem, mango, jackfruit and papaya” (Bond 44). The narrator loves to climb the trees and also enjoys the fruits that grow in the trees. His grandfather has planted many varieties of trees like peepul, neem, mango, jackfruit and papaya, and the narrator enjoys climbing the trees and enjoying the appetizing fruits from the trees. His grandfather has also planted a banyan tree which is the home for many animals and birds. Even though the banyan tree has thick branches and looks rough on the outside, it is the home for many creatures. In *Thirukkural*, Valluvar brings out the importance of trees in the life of humans, whereas in the article titled, “Thiruvalluvar’s Observation on Nature: A Study on the Classical Tamil Text *Thirukkural*”, Kalaiarsan remarks:

Valluvar mentioned about the trees and plants in his work. He used *Maruthu Maram*, the tree which cures the illness of people by providing its air, shadow, leaves, tender fruits, leaves, aerial roots. The tree offers what it needs, though it is in deep forest, “A tree that fruits in th’hamlet’s central mart; Is wealth that falls to men of liberal heart (Kural 216).” (419)

In both the short stories, the theme representation of nature is finely depicted through the surroundings of the story which represents the love for nature and where people and nature have to depend on each other for the well-being of the world.

Findings of the research

Integral Role of Agriculture in Small-Town Life:

1. Agriculture and farming form the backbone of small-town communities, providing sustenance, economic stability, and cultural identity.
2. Both Alice Munro and Ruskin Bond depict characters deeply involved in agricultural activities, emphasizing the significance of cultivating crops and tending to livestock for personal sustenance.
3. The texts highlight how farming isn't merely a profession but a way of life, fostering a strong connection between individuals, their land, and their livelihoods.

Nature's Representation and Integration in Small-Town Existence:

1. Small-town settings, as portrayed in literature, showcase a deep intertwining of nature into daily life, contrasting with urban areas.
2. Characters like Nancy in Munro's stories and various individuals in Bond's narratives demonstrate an inherent appreciation for nature, longing to reside in environments rich with natural beauty.
3. Nature isn't just a backdrop but an essential element of identity, with small-town inhabitants cherishing their gardens, lakes, forests, and the flora and fauna that surround them.

Environmental Conservation and Interdependence:

1. The texts highlight a strong theme of environmental preservation within small-town communities.
2. Both Munro's and Bond's stories show characters deeply connected to the environment, either through their homes surrounded by nature or their active involvement in nurturing trees, gardens, and fields.
3. Additionally, there's an emphasis on the symbiotic relationship between humans and nature, echoing the sentiment that caring for the environment leads to mutual well-being.

These findings collectively underscore the significance of agriculture, the integration of nature into daily life, and the importance of environmental conservation within the small-town narrative landscape presented in the analyzed texts.

Conclusion

To conclude, Alice Munro and Ruskin Bond's literary works and Valluvar's *Thirukkural* have shown a rich tapestry of narratives that use nature and agricultural settings as meaningful backgrounds to portray deeper ideas and emotions. Farming and agriculture play an important role in the life of the people, where they serve as the source of living. The biocentric approach proposes the importance of both nature and man in the welfare of the world. While Munro and Bond share a strong love of nature and the rhythms of country life, their cultural and geographical backgrounds have influenced their distinct viewpoints. Likewise, Valluvar's depiction of nature and the role of farming in his Kurals have a deep impact on the readers that also represents the importance of man and nature relationships. Hence, Alice Munro and Ruskin Bond's works have the concepts of biocentricism and can be

studied further for long-scale research. It may help to turn modern-day man to realise the profound importance of nature in their lives.

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தமிழ்மொழி மற்றும் இலக்கிய பன்னாட்டு ஆய்விதழ்

அறிஞர்களால் மதிப்பீடு செய்யப்படும் அரையாண்டு பன்னாட்டு ஆய்விதழ்

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